

ISic1638

I.Sicily inscription 1638

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S. Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Domna fidelissima fem(ina) marina ş,ą,p[ientiaemirae] patrici
2. teoduli in pace d[ie] kall(endas) mart(ias)

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1895

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 494038

EDCS 12700066

Bibliography

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